

*Reflecting the Decolonial Turn in Comparative Law:
Comparative Comparative Legal Theory and the Challenge of Recolonialism –
The Annexes*

The Report for the United States for Topic 2, General Theory and Legal Philosophy
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Topic 2. Théorie générale du droit et philosophie du droit/General legal theory and legal philosophy

The Decolonial Turn in Comparative Law / Le virage décolonial en droit comparé

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Reporters for the United States

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The International Academy of Comparative Law meets every four years in one of the states in which it has a national organizational member. Founded in The Hague in 1924, as a body of scholars who would collaboratively study the legal systems of all of the nations of the Earth through comparative perspectives, the Academy's purpose is to foster greater understanding among those nations to encourage cooperation among them that might bring a lasting peace.

Toward that end, the comparative legal society of the host nation identifies arenas for study and identifies an expert in each arena to serve as its *Rapporteur général*, who frames enquiries for the national organizations to answer *via* reports presented at the following Congress. The national organizations commission national reporters who are familiar with the particular arena of study to conduct the appropriate review of comparative scholarship

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and law in their country, usually over the preceding decade, and to prepare a general narrative report as well as specific answers to the *Rapporteur's* questions.

The American Society of Comparative Law serves this role in the United States and publishes its reports in a quadrennial supplement to its *American Journal of Comparative Law*, published for it by Oxford University Press. The general report on Topic 2 will be found there. However, given the complexity of the topic assigned, the length of the report with its annexes necessitates the separate publication of the annexes in some accessible repository. Thus, the annexes are placed here (and, potentially, in other digital scholarly repositories).

This format also allows for this publication to provide an unusual benefit to the reader, which is to include the content of the general survey as well as the answers of the national reporters for the U.S. to the prompts of the survey. The inclusion of the whole survey not only conveys essential context for the answers but also conveys a broader expression of the scope of the Congress's chosen topic and of the topic's significance to the legal systems, politics, and cultures of nations across the Earth.

These Annexes present, in Annex One, the General Remarks and Questionnaire, formulated by Professor Pasa, incorporated with the United States report's responses. Professor Pasa's General Remarks will be followed by Profs. Sheppard's and Hoeflich's introductory and concluding remarks. Professor Pasa's questions will each be followed by their answers.

Annex Two presents an empirical bibliography of scholarship identified in the process of this research as indicative (though not exhaustive) of the American scholarly work related to the matters raised in the Questionnaire. It aggregates and characterizes scholarship related to decolonial theory and its allied schools of thought, written in the last decade by scholars based in or affiliated with U.S. institutions, or as published in the *American Journal of Comparative Law*.

Following Annex Two are several elaborations of concepts in the Report that might interest some specialists, or the intellectual curiosity gatherer.

Annex One: The General Remarks, Questionnaire, and Responses

I. The General Remarks

The questionnaire is directed at scholars from diverse geographical backgrounds who employ varying theoretical approaches to examine the intersections between law and the legacies of colonialism. Its primary objective is to assess whether a decolonial turn in comparative law is currently unfolding – paralleling similar shifts in other academic disciplines – and to explore the implications of such a transformation, given the complexity of colonial legal experiences across different jurisdictions. This complexity manifests not only at an ontological level, concerning the very nature of colonialism, but more significantly from a phenomenological perspective, emphasizing lived experiences and intersubjective as well as interstate relations.

Historically, certain nations or territories were colonized while others were not. In some instances, populations successfully engaged in rebellion, whereas in others, colonial elites asserted independence while maintaining colonial structures in their countries – at least until recent times. Law, like other facets of human life, has undergone a degree of Westernization in all these places. Despite these transformations having occurred in the past, it remains pertinent to ask what elements of these colonial legacies persist today, and whether these influence comparative law, too.

Colonization was not only a power dynamic manifested on the ground, but also an ideological framework that categorized some societies as inferior and others as superior. This questionnaire seeks to investigate the intellectual tools available today to address this phenomenon from a legal perspective. Are we currently witnessing a new era of decolonial structuring in legal research and analysis? Or do alternative conceptual frameworks – such as postcolonial or anticolonial positionalities – provide a more precise lens through which to examine these issues?

In practical terms, this questionnaire aims to gather valuable insights into this decolonial turn, should such a phenomenon indeed be occurring. It endeavors to facilitate an understanding of the issue at municipal, regional, and supranational levels, thereby mapping the current ‘state of the art’ in this field. To engage with this question critically, it is essential to reflect on the suffix “-colonial” and its connotations. What does it precisely signify? What constituted colonial law? Historically, colonial law encompassed the legal frameworks

governing colonization — particularly the relationships between the metropolitan power and the colonized territories — as well as the legal regimes applicable to both metropolitan and colonial subjects. However, in many jurisdictions, colonial law has neither been an autonomous discipline nor an explicit subject of legal discourse, except in a veiled manner.

This survey thus seeks to recover colonial traces dispersed across various legal domains — constitutional law, private law, criminal law, commercial law, cultural heritage law, and others — to establish a theoretical and comparative framework for reconstructing the debate. Scholars working within the TWAAIL (Third World Approaches to International Law) paradigm have extensively explored these issues. More recently, the convergence of differentiated theoretical perspectives — including the sociology of law, legal history and philosophy, cultural and social anthropology, ethnographic methodologies, intersectionality critique, and militant legal anthropology — has played a significant role in shaping the epistemologies of the South. These approaches acknowledge and validate anti-capitalist, anti-colonial, and anti-patriarchal legal experiences.

Furthermore, the concept of pluriversality and its various articulations — which assert the legitimacy of multiple traditions and social orderings — offers a potential theoretical foundation for decolonial epistemologies that seek to transcend the modern matrix of coloniality. Even within the framework of transitional justice, many of history's marginalized groups have sought legal recognition of the injustices they have endured under colonial regimes, either directly or indirectly. They have often identified State structures as the closest successors to the original perpetrators of wrongful acts or as systemic enforcers of regimes of domination and subjugation.

While some States have acknowledged the darker aspects of their colonial past — at least in international relations — by addressing historical claims and resolving lingering conflicts, the reconciliation presumed to have been achieved frequently remains illusory or incomplete.

Several factors contribute to this. Cultural, political, social, and economic considerations have significantly impeded efforts to confront the colonial and racist past of many societies. This persistent colonial amnesia might be sustained by the enduring dominance of Eurocentric perspectives, including concerns over maintaining the Euro-Atlantic geopolitical balance, which may have obstructed a full appreciation of colonialism's systemic effects. One pertinent question could also be whether other types of domination have given rise to analogous problems, as the history of empires is not exclusively concerned with the imposition of Western law. Additionally, various so-called technical legal obstacles further complicate reconciliation with the past. These include the principle of State immunity, as recognized in international law (a remnant of the doctrine that the 'King can do

no wrong'), statutes of limitations, and the principle of *tempus regit actum* (whereby events and actions are assessed according to the legal framework in force at the time they occurred, even if they were then considered lawful or mandatory).

Further challenges arise from evidentiary difficulties in proving historical facts in court and establishing causality — particularly given the prolonged time spans between wrongful acts and the harms for which redress is sought. These legal constraints partially explain why existing legal mechanisms often fail to adequately address the needs of victims as individuals, as well as the broader challenges of decolonizing, decommodifying, and depatriarchalizing modern legal frameworks, including constitutional Charters and civil, criminal, and procedural Codes.

Thus far, decolonizing juridical thought and legal practice — if indeed this process is underway — necessitates a critical examination of legal systems' historical contexts by deconstructing colonial legacies embedded within legal categories, such as subjective rights and legal personhood. This effort also entails challenging legal rules governing property, ownership, possession, contracts, and torts by engaging with Indigenous and non-colonial legal traditions. Furthermore, it requires a reassessment of core legal principles, including public policy (*ordre public*), *bonnes mœurs*, and, ultimately, democracy and the rule of law.

Additionally, renewed scrutiny of legal education and methodologies — their rigor as well as their limitations — would be instrumental in advancing critical comparative and international legal studies on this subject.

The overarching aim is to construct a repertoire of collective memories — albeit fragmented and incomplete — as these networks of memory may ensure the transmission of historical consciousness across generations. This effort seeks to mitigate the risk of monumentalizing individual or identity-based collective memories, a concern widely reflected in scholarly literature. Ultimately, this inquiry holds the potential to reshape not only our understanding and practice of comparative law but also our engagement with broader questions of justice, power, and equality in a global context.

We thus invite you to participate in this questionnaire and, in doing so, by drawing on examples from your experience as a jurist engaging (or not) in dialogue with alternative epistemological frameworks.

The questionnaire is divided into three sections: Theories, Data, and Experiences. Within each section, respondents are asked either to collect and present data on the debate — where applicable in the Rapporteur's country — or to provide their personal perspectives on the subject matter.

II. The Introduction and Conclusion of the Report for the United States

A. The Introduction.

The *Rapporteur général* for legal philosophy, Professor Barbara Pasa of Università Iuav di Venezia, created an informative and provocative survey on decolonialist writing and theory in comparative legal scholarship. The survey's questions and our answers for the United States were provided to Professor Pasa as was our decennial review of decolonialist theory and subjects in U.S. comparative legal scholarship. . . .

For this National Report, we synthesized our scholarship review with our responses to Professor Pasa's survey, then explored why we suspect we reached our conclusions: Specifically, we believe U.S. comparative legal scholars will contribute profound advancements to the field. Yet, we do not believe decolonialist theory will supplant existing comparative and critical methods among U.S. comparative legal scholars.

B. The Reporters' Conclusions and Observations

Many Americans embrace decolonialist ideas, and many more would do so if these concepts and those of associated groups were more widely discussed in general culture. Yet, American culture is torn across myriad seams of the national fabric. Very few U.S. citizens see the longest, most frayed rips that are legacies of colonialism. Few of those who do recognize the damage as borne of the hierarchies of colonization.

We realize that the United States, and other states of the Global North, have increasingly appeared negligent in the practice of their customary rubrics assuring the people of just governance and fair opportunity. It is a rare day with no news of erosion from political gluttony, private greed, and official cowardice, each a symptom of the failure of trust in legal institutions by their own leaders. The collapse of that trust, whether by the officials or citizens, is symptomatic of mortal decline of the legal system, as a whole. That much can be seen by comparativists who favor either customary or decolonialist analysis. Indeed, each might tardily race to avoid upheaval from what either might see as the revival of thieving hierarchies – what both might call recolonialism.

Americans are barraged with colonial echoes in America's distinct legacies of slavery by law or in fact, of native displacement and cultural destruction, of the vicious marginalization of American citizens and immigrants descended from families from Mexico or elsewhere in the global South, and of an ever-twisting kaleidoscope of sex-obsessed discrimination. Yet a persistent slosh of political avarice pays for endless sources of deception and doubt, so that nearly as many Americans might praise such legacies as

condemn them. Such assaults on truth and fairness in U.S. political and legal culture are readily identifiable by comparativists or legal analysts favoring any techniques, though the decolonialist might have the most robust toolkit for the work

To raise historical arguments about the colonial dynamic can be confusing to the American Twitterverse, owing not just to our globally shortening attention spans but also to the persistence of the U.S. colonial view. Americans, after all, still see the colonists as if they were natives and we are their beleaguered heirs (even if election among the candidates to be our tormentors is highly contentious). The larger rips through that cloth persist, exposing issues of wealth, race, color, nationality, religion, and – increasingly – politics. These immediate conditions of discrimination, exploitation, false narratives, and genuine harm – often but not always linked to unearned economic, social and political power – need no arguments from history to allure or to fear.

We, the Reporters, believe the arguments of the decolonialist turn have great merit. Yet, we understand if U.S. scholars (including comparative lawyers) hesitate to hoist the ensigns of TWAIL, post-colonialism, or decolonialism as high up the mast as those of Critical Race Theory, Feminist Jurisprudence, or the critical arguments most deeply embedded in American culture: Freedom, Justice, Equality, and the Rule of Law.

We strongly suspect that, for this and the next generation, our arguments will be grounded in very recent history and in present efforts to reject the objectively false narratives that amount to what, in this context, is recolonialism. Yet in every regard, we believe that scholars and the public should be aware of past evils, learn from such evils, be guided by the necessity to avoid them, and thus be neither dominated by them nor driven to vengeance because by them, lest the corruption of the past forever corrode the future. The evergreen question is therefore not what happened to cause injustice, but what is causing injustice. The answer to that question more likely to be a defensible basis for social change than any answer derived from the misconduct of prior generations.

C. Prompts and Answers to the General Reporter's Questionnaire

Theories

A. The 'decolonial turn': setting the scene

1) How much do the claims of coloniality/de-post-anti-coloniality represent a recognizable legal debate in your country? Please add references to the sources you used (quoting authors, journals and reviews, monographs, treaties, *etc.*) in giving your answer.

Certain core texts of decoloniality, particularly Frantz Fanon's *A Dying Colonialism*, remain well known in the United States. Yet, until quite recently, very little legal or political discourse in the United States has been explicitly between colonial and decolonial values. Instead, the intersection of Tribal Law, federal laws and regulations affecting the tribes and nations, and general federal and state law often takes the decolonial turn. See Report, part III.

We believe the most significant reason for this seeming disinterest in coloniality is the focus in the U.S. on discrimination on the basis of race, gender, nationality, color, age, and disability. This focus has resulted from nearly two centuries of intermittent efforts to assure "equal protection of the laws" and to eradicate the vestiges of "the badges and incidents of slavery." These efforts have taken many forms, including the revival of dormant constitutional protection, as in the *Brown* case, the revision of laws such as the Civil Rights Acts of the twentieth century, and cultural efforts to tell stories of oppression and injustice more accurately and candidly, as in the opening of two museums in the Smithsonian Institution. These efforts have been resonant with decolonialist hostility to illegitimate hierarchy, unequal protection of the laws, and alienating and oppressive laws, generally and particularly when directed at marginalized groups.

Thus, decolonial analysis and argument were rare in legal or political arguments beyond what in 2026, is still formally known as "American Indian Law." However, sudden and far-reaching changes in federal policy ordered by President Donald J. Trump have provoked new legal arguments dealing with discrimination on the basis of race, color, or nationality that are, now, increasingly argued in the previously incompatible languages of the settler and the colonized. This will likely open a new window for decolonialist argument.

2) Could you please indicate which of the following terms you believe to be the most appropriate for describing/critiquing our contemporary times: post-colonial, anti-colonial or decolonial?

In the United States, the times cannot be fully described by one choice: we see them as a hybrid of colonial, decolonial, and recolonial.

3) Is a 'decolonial critique' necessary to understand our contemporary lives?

We believe the answer to this question is situationally contingent. The variety of causes and forms of immigration to the United States, both during the colonial period and over two and a half centuries since Independence suggests the decolonial critique is not necessary to understand all contemporary lives in the United States. But, this observation would not suggest the decolonial critique is not beneficial, perhaps, even essential to understanding many of them.

3, cont.) To what extent should ethical convictions, philosophical principles, economic reasoning, religious rules, cultural bias and/or other aspects be considered in this debate?

To the extent that a coherent definition and method for those tools can be articulated with sufficient clarity and utility that parties on either side of the debate would share a common understanding of the tools and would each be able to use such tools to explain fairly and accurately their position in such arguments.

4) What measures can be implemented to strengthen our methodological tools while achieving decolonial objectives in our research?

Emphasize arguments that are compatible with the Romanticized view of American settler culture, which values liberty of thought, free expression, equality of treatment before the law, equality of opportunity, and public and governmental care sufficient to avoid failures of access to health, nutrition, and education. Avoid arguments based on the colonial past, altogether. In the United States, the colonial dynamics of the Indian Wars that ended 150 years ago are in no way as persuasive to require full tax-funded support for reservation services and other support as are the continued failure to meet treaty obligations, coupled with native communities' persistent health and economic challenges. The most successful arguments have presented careful explication of causation from some sequence of specific repressive or exploitive colonial actions to a present institutional actor or beneficiary.

This is the key to law cases brought under the Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act, Pub. L. 101-601, 104 Stat. 3048 (1990) is codified at 25 U.S.C. 3001 *et seq.*, NAGPRA requires federal agencies and federally funded museums to return Native American or Hawai'ian objects that the agency or museum possesses that are elements of the cultural patrimony, funerary objects, or sacred objects removed from the land or possession of the native people.

5) With regard to the entry points of 'coloniality' in teaching comparative law, please could you outline your thoughts?

In teaching comparative law, the point must remain comparing the laws of contrasting legal systems, even if those systems are in the same nation at different times. We see no reason *not* to use tools associated with the decolonial turn in either analysis of one system or another or for their comparison. In that endeavor, comparing laws regulating similar conduct in a legal system influenced by a colonial past to such laws in a legal system that had no colonial experience might have considerable value to the decolonial movement.

6) Do you believe there is a connection between the classification and shaping of legal systems and 'colonial legacies'?

Yes, when the history of a given legal system suggests that it has such a legacy. Even so, two qualifications are critical.

First, one must realize that nearly every modern nation was once a colony of (or was similarly subordinate to) some other state. The question -- is there a legacy from the colonial experience on the current legal system -- does not depend on proximity or distance in time but on the persistence of influence of the colonial culture, economy, laws, *etc.*, on conditions in the present.

Second, the analyst cannot ignore the likelihood of native transgressions and exploitative behavior that preceded contact with pioneers, colonizers, and settlers from a colonial power. Care must be taken to avoid an ahistorical construction of the persons, language, religion, aesthetics, knowledge, skills, and culture lost to colonization, regardless of its wonderful or dismal truths.

7) Could you please elaborate on whether legal knowledge is being rethought and critiqued from a de/post/anti-colonial perspective, incorporating an intersectional critique to understand structural inequalities?

In the United States, this has occurred largely in a parallel context arising from a more general anti-discriminatory framework responding to racial, gender, and abilities discrimination.

7 cont.) Given your interests and research domains, could you offer some legal insights?

The current administration is expressly seeking to reverse efforts made following the Second World War, to confront the U.S. history of alienation, oppression, and exploitation.¹ Such efforts appear to have spurred a political response using arguments employing an analysis similar to decolonialism. As of this writing, however, the U.S. President has broadly challenged the American constitutional separation of powers and the international legal order. He has ordered what appear to be unprovoked armed attacks by the United States on Venezuela and Iran, while threatening similarly the sovereignty of Cuba and Denmark (as to Greenland), using tactics that are contrary to American military doctrine, regulations, and laws. Simultaneously, the President has ordered the hiring of a large domestic force of border police and assigned them idiosyncratic duties in American cities, while detaining and deporting thousands of persons lawfully in the United States. It is likely that these American actions of state will result in a revived discussion of America's legal and constitutional foundations, which is very likely to cross decolonialist lines.

¹ See, e.g., Executive Order, Ending Radical and Wasteful Government DEI Programs and Preferencing (January 20, 2025). Online at <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/01/ending-radical-and-wasteful-government-dei-programs-and-preferencing/> (Last visited on February 20, 2026); Executive Order Restoring Truth and Sanity To American History (March 27, 2025). Online at <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/03/restoring-truth-and-sanity-to-american-history/> (Last visited February 20, 2026). See also Letter to the Smithsonian: Review of Smithsonian Exhibitions and Materials (December 18, 2026). Online at <https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefings-statements/2025/12/letter-to-the-smithsonian-review-of-smithsonian-exhibitions-and-materials/> (Last visited on February 20, 2026).

Data

B. What is 'decolonial law'?

We believe “decolonialization” and “decolonialism,” represent not only a critical view of colonial legal systems but also an ideology for the identification of, and opposition to, illegitimate hierarchical structures of all kinds. We agree with and have adopted the opening narrative of the General Reporter’s questionnaire in this regard. See part I of the narrative report. “Decolonial law” is, therefore, a change in law that remediates or eliminates such hierarchies or their legal, economic, social, or cultural effects.

1) Could you please provide a brief overview of the historical and institutional context of the phenomenon, with particular reference to whether your country was a ‘colonial empire’, part of a ‘colonial empire’, a colonial protectorate, or a related legal entity?

The United States was once thirteen English colonies that incorporated formerly Dutch, Swedish, French, Spanish, and Russian colonies as well as vast Indigenous lands while welcoming immigrants from across the globe . It has become a colonial empire. Please see part II, in the narrative report.

2) With regard to regulatory interventions, it would be useful to know if they are general or sectoral. Could you please provide details of international instruments that are aimed at regulating residual relations between former colonies and former metropolises?

As to internal colonies, statutes such as the Northwest Ordinance (1787) and the Kansas-Nebraska Act (1854) regulated specific aspects of colonial development and laws.² As to the treatment of Indigenous Nations and Tribes, a cycle of cession by

²The Northwest Ordinance detailed the territorial development of lands northwest of the Ohio River, patently organizing departments to manage immigration and later made states, on lands owned by the Shawnee (in southern Ohio), the Delaware (Lenape) and the Kickapoo (in Indiana) the Miami (the center of the territory in Indiana and Michigan), the Potawatomi (Michigan and Wisconsin), as well as large groups of Wyandot (Huron), Ottawa, Mingo, Seneca, and Cherokee, most of whom joined the Western Confederacy to oppose settlement west of the Ohio River. Nonetheless, Article 3 of the statute provided,

[T]he utmost good faith shall always be observed towards the Indians; their lands and property shall never be taken from them without their consent; and, in their property, rights, and liberty, they shall never be invaded or disturbed, unless in just and lawful wars authorized by Congress; but laws founded in justice and humanity, shall from time to time be made for preventing wrongs being done to them, and for preserving peace and friendship with them.

An Ordinance for the Government of the Territory of the United States Northwest of the River Ohio, July 13, 1787, House Document No. 398, Documents Illustrative of the Formation of the Union of the American States, Charles C. Tansill, ed. (Government Printing Office, 1927).

An Act to Organize the Territories of Nebraska and Kansas, 10 Stat. 277 (1854), created two territories on the then-western border of the U.S., allowing the settlers to vote to allow or forbid slavery, unleashing considerable violence between abolitionists and slavers, though both territories eventually were admitted as free states.

treaty, coercion, resistance, and conquest is very briefly described in part II, in the narrative report.

Could you also state which conventions your country has entered into (e.g. Yaoundé, Lomé, etc.) to foster commercial, industrial, agricultural, etc. cooperation?

As to external colonies, United Nations Security Council Resolution 21, of July 18, 1947, created the Trust Territory of the Pacific Islands (TTPI) and made the U.S. the trustee for over 2,000 former Japanese-mandated islands, with the understanding that the U.S. would build military bases on some of the islands. The trust was dissolved in phases, with independent statehood for the Marshall Islands (1986), then the Federated States of Micronesia and Northern Mariana Islands (1986), and Palau (1994). The remainder are unincorporated territories of the United States.

3) Is there any law in your country today that is designed to make former colonies independent and to help them become self-sufficient politically and economically? And how has the indigenous legal tradition changed since independence?

As to internal colonies, for the last century, the U.S. Congress has intermittently passed statutes to ameliorate the conditions of the native tribes and nations on reservations, and individual natives not on reservations. The classic summary of these laws is still *Cohen's Manual*.³ The laws are codified in Title 25 of the United States Code and include:

- Snyder Act (1921): Bureau of Indian Affairs (BIA) must use federal funds for services to native tribes.
- Indian Citizenship Act (1924): All U.S.-born American Indians and Alaska Natives are full U.S. citizens.
- Indian Reorganization Act (IRA) ("The Indian New Deal") (1934): Ended forced divisions of tribal lands, restored some lands to some tribes, and encouraged each Nation and Tribe to adopt a constitution and a tribal council.
- Indian Civil Rights Act (1968): The U.S. Bill of Rights extended to persons under tribal jurisdictions.
- Indian Self-Determination and Education Assistance Act (1975): Federal funds and programs in health and education moved under tribal authorities rather than federal management.

³FELIX COHEN, HANDBOOK OF FEDERAL INDIAN LAW (1941, Neil Jessup, Kenneth J. Washburn, Gregory Abalvsky, *et al.*, eds. , 2024).

- Indian Child Welfare Act (1978): Federal law bars state laws that divided Native or removed Native children from the families' homes and cultures.
- American Indian Religious Freedom Act (1978): Federal rights for Tribes and persons to protect access to sacred sites and to practice traditional religions.
- Indian Gaming Regulatory Act (1988): National Indian Gaming Commission created to regulate tribal casinos and gaming, with or without the agreement of the local state government.
- Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act (1990): Human remains, funerary objects, and cultural items held by federal agencies or federally funded museums to be repatriated to existing tribes.
- Tribal Self-Governance Act (1994): Expanded self-governance, allowing tribes broader control over federal funding and services.
- Violence Against Women Act Reauthorization (2022): Jurisdiction over these federal crimes extended to Tribes enforcing criminal law on tribal land.

On the other hand, see *Arizona v. Navajo Nation*, 599 U.S. 555 (2023), in which a majority of the Supreme Court ruled a United States treaty with the Navajo Nation gave the nation water rights but did not require the U.S. Government to take affirmative steps to provide the water. Justice Gorsuch filed a memorable dissent.

4) It is important to consider whether there are legal instruments in place that mandate reparation or restitution by the state or private entities involved in violations of human rights. Alternatively, is it the courts, through their interpretation, that offer reparation?

In U.S. law, the term "human rights" usually connotes internationally recognized individual rights, while "civil rights" connotes federally recognized individual rights, whether they are established under the U.S. Constitution or by statute. Civil rights first recognized judicially are sometimes embedded, later, in a constitutional or statutory right.

The most essential federal statutes protecting individual rights were enacted after the Civil War and during the Civil Rights Era. They are codified in Title 42 of the U.S. Code.

States may also recognize additional, specific civil rights that provide legal process for their enforcement, which is particularly important for the enforcement of rights in family law.

Any person may seek judicial relief in state or federal court to prevent an impending harm or to receive restitution for a past harm, caused by a violation of that person's civil rights by a state official or private person acting as an agent of the state, However, the federal courts have limited the capacity of courts to hear many of these cases under various statutes of limitations as well as the judicial doctrines of "abstention" from actions already heard in a state court, of "qualified immunity" of officials for acts within the scope of their office that are not patently unlawful, and prudential rules, such as the "standing" requirement that a plaintiff have suffered a specific injury distinct from the harm to other citizens.

A different process is available for a person who claims to be wrongfully detained by a government officer, which is the process of *habeas corpus*, assured in the Constitution and enforced under Title 28 of the U.S. Code.

5) Could you please provide information on whether there are any effective reputational sanctions, memorial policies and practices, in place in your country that would encourage the parties to reach an out-of-court settlement regarding the wrongs suffered?

Yes. Several processes lead to pre-trial settlement. First, the likelihood that the defendant is covered by an insurance policy makes likely the insurer will participate early in a dispute arising from an allegation of the violation of a civil right. Insurers prefer to settle cases that they are likely to lose in court or whose defense in court will cost more than the cost of compensation. Second, most courts now require mediation of disputes prior to a trial, although that process would, by the time court-ordered mediation is scheduled, have already made the dispute a matter of public record.

6) What effect do they have, for example, on the resignification of cultural heritage, lands regimes, environmental protections, family and personal relationships? In other words, which sectors of your legal system (civil, criminal, administrative, constitutional, commercial laws, etc.) are affected?

As to confidential settlements of disputes involving violations of the law, like an environmental crime or an act of physical abuse within a family, the initial response to a report of such an event is likely to be by administrative agents or municipal police, who will follow procedures of investigation and citation for unlawful acts, which are obligated to be of public record.

Public entities that are, or whose agents are, accused of violating civil rights often negotiate settlements that are approved by the responsible executive officer or governing body, like a state attorney general, county commission, or city council, in quasi-private meetings often called “executive session.” Those negotiations might have been direct dialogues between counsel for the parties or by mediation, but the approval of a remedy without a court order is likely, either way. Many of these remain unknown to the public.

Disputes that do not involve a specific violation of law, such as the resignification of a cultural heritage site, are unlikely to be treated as legal matters but are likely to be seen as political matters.

7) Are there any signs of continuity or discontinuity with the colonial past?

Yes. Please see Part II of the narrative report.

Experiences

C. What was and is ‘colonial law’?

1) Colonial law: was it a set of rules of the metropolitan state that your country recognised? Was it a separate subject that legal science in your country recognised (and for example, had legal science studied the law that was in force in what later became colonies or protectorates)?

In the English colonies of North America, colonial law was distinct for each colony. As English colonies, the common law of England was applied in colonial courts; however, it was subject to alteration by the colonial charter then in force, whether the charter was issued directly by the crown or by a proprietor who, essentially, owned the colony, such as William Penn and Pennsylvania. During the earliest years of the colony, the governor and a small council of elites would make additional laws, the combination of all of these laws dealing with local matters. Beginning in the early eighteenth century, such laws would be passed by a colonial legislative assembly or, as in the Commonwealth of Virginia, by a House of Burgesses.

There was little legal science in the English colonies until late in the eighteenth century, when judges such as Judge Tapping Reeve began, in 1774, to organize

Connecticut and English law to teach in a small building he built as a law school in the side yard of his house in Litchfield, Connecticut, or when Chancellor George Wythe began to organize Virginia and English law to teach the law at the College of William and Mary, commencing in 1780. What legal science there was amounted to synthesis of the English common law with colonial charters, local legislative acts, and judicial precedents.⁴

2) Sources such as custom have been transcribed, but these were often rules that did not lend themselves to being verbalised by stating the elements that make up the relevant legal case. How did transcription change these rules? Can you give an example?

In U.S. law, this occurred and still occurs mainly in state private law. The classic example is the reduction of the principle of negligence, a harm caused to one person by the act of another person who broke the general duty to act with due care and attention. Thanks to treatise writers, statutes, written court opinions, and – in the 1920s a national but private group of scholars and lawyers, the American Law Institute – specific situations of negligence were reduced to elements of a tort that could be pled in court against the alleged tortfeasor. In some cases, actions were harder to maintain, in others easier, but in all, out-of-court settlement was easier to obtain, because the written elements of the tort of negligence would also serve as the instructions to a jury to guide their consideration of the evidence. The reduction of the idea of negligence to a sequence of written rules of pleading and evidence also had the effect of levelling the influence of counsel on the outcome of the case, as such arguments became less dependent on the art of persuasion.

3) Are there any studies on the survival or decline of pre-colonial law? Is this research commissioned by the state or by universities? Has colonial law disappeared from the colonies without transformation, or has it merged into another discipline without clear boundaries?

The persistence of pre-colonial law into state law in the U.S. continues to be a matter of research in some matters in legal practice, most notably in land law. In general, pre-colonial laws that persist were adopted by colonial law and merged into early state laws.

⁴ See WILLIAM E. NELSON, *THE COMMON LAW IN COLONIAL AMERICA* (4 vols.) (2018) and PETER CHARLES HOFFER, *LAW AND PEOPLE IN COLONIAL AMERICA* (2019).

A fascinating question, however, persists regarding the influence of pre-colonial law on the organization of the colonies into the United States. The Law of the Great Peace, a constitutional settlement among the Haudenosaunee, or the Iroquois Federation, located mainly in or near what is now the Hudson River valley, influenced Benjamin Franklin to organize an assembly in Albany, New York, in 1765, and it appears to have had a continuing influence in the Declaration of 1776 and the Convention of 1787.⁵ This premise was, until recently, little known and strongly contested. It has, however, been embraced by documentary film-maker Ken Burns in *The American Revolution* (2025).⁶

4) What are the vestiges of colonial law in your country? Describe institutions, rules and/or principles with a colonial legacy.

The legacies of colonial law and its institutions are most visible in the states formed from the original colonies, where courthouses and legislative buildings reflected English models, and where the colonial law was generally received as state law until modified by a state's legislature. Though less obvious, the same legacy has been transmitted to the U.S. territories and to the states formed from them, by duplication of the patterns of legal institutions from older states, usually through migration of lawyers from the old states to the new territories.⁷

5) What is the relationship with local customary law? And with religious law? And how is the clash between local customary, religious and colonial rules resolved in practice?

Local customary law influenced local laws, predominately, through the presence of citizen juries as the finders of fact in civil and in criminal trials in federal and state courts. Religious law may be pled in U.S. courts only as the basis of a contract-like arrangement among members of the a given religion, particularly in disputes over property owned by churches, temples, or other religious institutions. The Establishment Clause of the First Amendment prohibits religious laws from being a basis of legal enforcement or judicial decisions.

⁵ See, e.g., BRUCE E. JOHANSEN, *FORGOTTEN FOUNDERS: BENJAMIN FRANKLIN, THE IROQUOIS, AND THE RATIONALE FOR THE AMERICAN REVOLUTION* (Gambit Publishers, 1982).

⁶ See Ken Burns, Sarah Botstein & David Schmid, *The American Revolution*, at <https://www.pbs.org/kenburns/the-american-revolution>. See also Geoffrey C. Ward & Ken Burns, *The American Revolution, An Intimate History* (2025).

⁷ See M. H. Hoeflich & Stephen Sheppard, *The Mystery of the Leavenworth Oaths*, 71 U. Kan. L. Rev. 751 (2023).

6) Is there a latent (neo)colonial law?

Yes. Please see Part III of the general Report.

7) Is military force as a mode of conflict resolution a (neo)colonial legacy?

Not at this time. It is prohibited by the Posse Comitatus Act of 1878, codified at 18 U.S.C. § 1385.

7, cont.) Is the inviolability of borders a (neo)colonial theme?

Yes.

7 cont.) Is the charisma of traditional leaders or the military caste [an influence that] can be outweighed by that of those who have control of data and information?

This is a critical question for the contemporary United States, particularly in the light of the rise of public political engagement by tech billionaires, whose wealth might lead voters to see them in a charismatic frame and who also control the infrastructure of data and information. We believe that the answer to this question is presently unknown.

Annex Two: Representative Decolonial Scholarship in

U.S. Comparative Law, 2015-2025

Note: In anticipation of this report, a survey was conducted of U.S.-based scholarly and legal databases, searching for papers, articles, and books of comparative-law research that discussed or applied decolonialism in their analysis, between 2015 and 2025, written by authors in U.S. institutions or published in the *American Journal of Comparative Law*. Though the ever-present potential of timing or error suggest this effort will have overlooked some works, we believe the results are at least suggestive of the output of U.S. comparative law research employing decolonialist methods. These materials include 64 scholars generating 89 individual writings. The scholars were divided among three predominate categories of topics: (1) American Indian Law or otherwise concerning governmental treatment of Indigenous Peoples, (2) constitutional or interstate comparative law, and (3) international comparative law.

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*** The Conclusion of Annex Two ***

III. Annex Three: Elaborations on Certain Points in the National Report

Elaboration A: On von Savigny's Embrace of Integrationist and Cultural Legal Comparativism

Savigny's historicist masterpiece, *On the Vocation of Our Age* ought not to be read without his earlier *Treatise on Possession*. Compare "For law, as for language, there is no moment of absolute cessation; it is subject to the same movement and development as every other popular tendency" FRIEDRICH CARL VON SAVIGNY, OF THE VOCATION OF OUR AGE FOR LEGISLATION AND JURISPRUDENCE 27 (Abraham Hayward trans., 1831), with "the right of possession consists simply in the claim of the possessor to be protected against . . . every disturbance of his physical control over the thing. . . . a right which belongs to every individual as a condition of his existence" FRIEDRICH CARL VON SAVIGNY, VON SAVIGNY'S TREATISE ON POSSESSION: OR THE *JUS POSSESSIONIS* OF THE CIVIL LAW 2-3 (Sir Erskine Perry trans., 1848). It is tough to maintain *only* a Functionalist argument or *only* an Integrationist or Culturalist argument, as Savigny's greatest pupil learned. Compare

The reception of foreign legal institutions is not a matter of nationality, but of usefulness and need. No one bothers to fetch a thing from afar when he has one as good or better at home, but only a fool would refuse quinine just because it didn't grow in his back garden.

RUDOLF VON JHERING, *GEIST DES RÖMISCHEN RECHTS*, Part I 8-9 (Tony Weir, trans., 1852, 9th ed. 1955), with, "To attempt to understand the law of a people without its history and culture is to attempt to understand the effect without the cause." *Id.* at pp. 14-20.

**Elaboration B: An Extremely Selective List of Way-Marker Texts Into the
Decolonialist Turn**

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Elaboration C: Colonial American Slavery & Its Long, Hollow Echoes

Neither the Dutch and English colonists' seventeenth-century challenges to survive during their "rightful" settlement nor their anger over sovereign exploitation could camouflage the colonists' own exploitations of natives and slaves. Any bridge over the yawning chasm between the U.S. colonial focus and the North American native facts is complicated -- indeed obscured -- by the enslavement and purchase of enslaved persons from Africa and the Caribbean colonies.

Slaves were stripped of their liberty, identity, language, culture, religion, and alienated from their resources.⁸ Slaves were involuntary settlers.

Nearing the end of the colonial period in the United States, slaves accounted for, perhaps, one-fifth of the population.⁹ Slaves were not the only non-natives involuntarily colonizing English North America. British indentured servants, often children, who were subject to seven (or more) years of *de facto* ownership, were often sold for service or resale in the colonies, and convicts were routinely sentenced to transportation to America, many remaining in peonage until their sentences were completed.¹⁰ Yet as pernicious as was such "white slavery" for a period of years, the horror of race-based slavery was a transcendent evil. Race-based, multi-generational enslavement brought into effect in most colonies long before independence,¹¹ forced the enslaved from abroad not only to become colonists by involuntarily entering the country as slaves but also denied their children freedom, because the children of slaves were likewise enslaved.¹²

In the Convention of 1787 to adopt a new Constitution, it was well known that many delegates from the north abhorred slavery, but the delegates from southern, slave states

⁸ See BETTY WOOD, *SLAVERY IN COLONIAL AMERICA, 1619-1776* (2005); JOHN SAMUEL HARPHAM, *THE INTELLECTUAL ORIGINS OF AMERICAN SLAVERY: ENGLISH IDEAS IN THE EARLY MODERN ATLANTIC WORLD* (2025). Of course, not all slaves in the English colonies were immigrants. See ALAN GALLAY, *INDIAN SLAVERY IN COLONIAL AMERICA* (2015).

⁹ The most common statistic for colonial slavery is the first U.S. Census, which in 1790 reported 694,280 enslaved people of a population of 3,893,635, or 17.8%. See U.S. Census Bureau, *Heads of Families at the First Census of the United States, Taken in the Year 1790: South Carolina* at p. 8 (1908). Online at <https://www2.census.gov/library/publications/decennial/1790/heads-of-families-south-carolina.pdf> (Last visited February 20, 2026).

¹⁰ See DON JORDAN & MICHAEL WALSH, *WHITE CARGO: THE FORGOTTEN HISTORY OF BRITAIN'S WHITE SLAVES IN AMERICA* (2008); RUSSELL R. MENARD, *MIGRANTS, SERVANTS AND SLAVES: UNFREE LABOR IN COLONIAL BRITISH AMERICA* (2001).

¹¹ As to the earliest importations of slaves by the Dutch West India Company, see ANDREA C. MOSTERMAN, *SPACES OF ENSLAVEMENT: A HISTORY OF SLAVERY AND RESISTANCE IN DUTCH NEW YORK* (New Netherland Institute Studies) (2025).

¹² WILMA KING, *STOLEN CHILDHOOD: SLAVE YOUTH IN NINETEENTH-CENTURY AMERICA* (1995).

would not join it without concessions to allow slavery's persistence. The result was an evil compromise, allowing slavery to be protected for twenty years from Congressional interference.¹³ The evil done then was clear to many, such as Gouverneur Morris, a delegate from New York and a drafter of the final documents. James Madison wrote Morris "never would concur in upholding domestic slavery. It was a nefarious institution--It was the curse of heaven on the States where it prevailed."¹⁴

1. The Legalization of Horror: From Smuggling to *The Antelope*

The federal government's 1807 bar on the importation of slaves barely affected the machinery of human trafficking; it merely drove the trade underground and increased the "risk premium" paid to slave smugglers. These years marked divergence between American and British laws. While *Somerset's Case* (1772)¹⁵ and the persistent William Wilberforce led to the abolition of the slave trade and Lord Melbourne's 1833 compromise in the timing of implementation ended slavery in British colonies,¹⁶ as Morris had feared, the United States remained bound for decades by that curse of heaven on the States.

The American protection of slavers became constitutional doctrine in *The Antelope* (1825). Appearing before the Supreme Court, Francis Scott Key (the Baltimore lawyer whose poem would form the lyrics of the national anthem) argued that the Africans found aboard the vessel were "property" by the laws of their captors. Chief Justice John Marshall agreed. Marshall, a Virginia slave-owner himself, infamously wrote that although slavery was "contrary to the law of nature," it was nevertheless "consistent with the law of nations" as practiced by sovereign states.¹⁷ This decision effectively made the courts accomplices to the slave traders, ensuring many thousands of Africans remained in bondage owing to their status as "cargo."¹⁸

¹³ U.S. Constitution, Art. I, sect. 9.

¹⁴ MAX FARRAND, ED., 2 RECORDS OF THE FEDERAL CONVENTION OF 1787, 221-23 (1937).

¹⁵ *Somerset v. Stewart*, (1772) 98 ER 499, 20 State Tr. 1, (1772) Lofft 1.

¹⁶ BROOKE NEWMAN, [THE CROWN'S SILENCE: THE HIDDEN HISTORY OF SLAVERY AND THE BRITISH MONARCHY](#) (2026).

¹⁷ [The Antelope](#), 23 U.S. (10 Wheat.) 66, 120 (1825). Marshall's self-interest in this and other slavery cases is detailed in Paul Finkelman's *Master John Marshall and the Problem of Slavery*, U.CHIL.REV. ONLINE, at <https://lawreview.uchicago.edu/online-archive/master-john-marshall-and-problem-slavery> (Last visited February 12, 2026). *See also* --, SUPREME INJUSTICE: SLAVERY IN THE NATION'S HIGHEST COURT (2018).

¹⁸ *See* JOHN T. NOONAN, JR., [THE ANTELOPE: THE ORDEAL OF THE RECAPTURED AFRICANS IN THE ADMINISTRATIONS OF JAMES MONROE AND JOHN QUINCY ADAMS](#) (1977); *see also* JONATHAN M. BRYANT, [DARK PLACES OF THE EARTH: THE VOYAGE OF THE SLAVE SHIP ANTELOPE](#) (2015).

2. Secession, Civil War, and the Mirage of Reconstruction

Despite the rise of Northern abolitionists, inspired by the likes of William Lloyd Garrison and Frederick Douglass, the internal slave trade flourished, abetted, again, by the Supreme Court, whose Chief Justice, Roger Taney, ruled that slaves held in the United States could not become free.¹⁹ A child of slaves, Taney wrote, belonged to a “a subordinate and inferior class of beings who had been subjugated by the dominant race, and, whether emancipated or not, yet remained subject to their authority, and had no rights or privileges but such as those who held the power and the Government might choose to grant them.”²⁰ In Abraham Lincoln’s presidential campaign debates, he exposed the rot at the heart of Taney’s arguments. Lincoln’s election thus prompted the Southern states to secede from the Union. Simply, Confederate secession was driven by an explicit, well documented desire to protect the property rights of slaveholders – a fact persistently rejected and camouflaged in mythologies written about the Lost Cause.²¹

The resulting Civil War lasted four years and cost 600,000 lives, about 4% of the U.S. male population.²² President Lincoln, after initially framing the war’s purpose as preserving the Union, later issued the Emancipation Proclamation, freeing slaves in rebel territory, and – in his address at Gettysburg cemetery – reframed the war’s purpose to finally establish abolition, constitutional equality, and liberty.²³ At the war’s end the Reconstruction Amendments (13th, 14th, and 15th) and the Civil Rights Acts²⁴ promised a decolonialist reality for Black Americans.

¹⁹ *Scott v. Sandford*, 60 U.S. (19 How.) 393 (1856).

²⁰ *Id.* at 404-05.

²¹ Champions of the Old South began revising stories of slavery, the Confederacy, and the war, before clearing the rubble from Atlanta. Their lies undermined Reconstruction, justified Jim Crow, thwarted equal protection of the laws, and justified Southern bigotry for over 150 years. See EDWARD ALFORD POLLARD, *THE LOST CAUSE, (etc.)* (1867). See, however, TY SEIDULE, ROBERT E. LEE AND ME: A SOUTHERNER’S RECKONING WITH THE MYTH OF THE LOST CAUSE (2021); ADAM H. DOMBY, *THE FALSE CAUSE: FRAUD, FABRICATION, AND WHITE SUPREMACY IN CONFEDERATE MEMORY* (2020).

²² Over 50,000 men died in just four days at Gettysburg. American Battlefield Trust, *Civil War Casualties: The Cost of War: Killed, Wounded, Captured, and Missing* (2023). Online at <https://www.battlefields.org/learn/articles/civil-war-casualties> (Last visited February 12, 2026).

²³ See GEORGE P. FLETCHER, *OUR SECRET CONSTITUTION: HOW LINCOLN REDEFINED AMERICAN DEMOCRACY* (2003).

²⁴ The Thirteenth Amendment outlaws slavery and involuntary servitude. The Fourteenth assures citizenship to every person born in the United States and that no person shall be denied due process of law or equal protection of the laws. The Fifteenth assures the right to vote. The Civil Rights Acts of 1866 and 1875 provide private rights of action to enforce those rights and for criminalization of acts in derogation of them. See 42 U.S.C. sects. 1980-2000a (codifying also the Voting Rights Act and Civil Rights Act of 1957, 1960, and 1968). The Voting Rights Act of 1965 is now codified at 52 U.S.C. sects. 10101 & 20701-20706.

That promise died with the Presidential Compromise of 1877, when Rutherford B. Hayes traded the rights of Black Americans for his presidency.²⁵ Buying Southern votes with the promise to remove federal troops from the South, he claimed restoring confederates to power would encourage “the united and harmonious efforts of both races, actuated by motives of mutual sympathy and regard.”²⁶ Instead, the restored antebellum elite swiftly disenfranchised freedmen and synthesized Jim Crow’s retrograde laws with its extralegal violence — a near-century of state-sponsored terror and the fiction of “separate but equal.”²⁷

3. The Civil Rights Movement and Persistent Backlash

The mid-twentieth century saw a sustained legal assault on the Jim Crow regime as well as the unnamed and usually unacknowledged laws and customs prevailing in many Northern cities, spearheaded in both arenas by the NAACP Legal Defense Fund²⁸ and supported by a network of civil-rights litigators and academics, who continued to fight in such cases into the 1990s.²⁹ From the proscription of white-family exemptions from statutory burdens on voting rights³⁰ to the 1950 desegregation of law schools³¹ to the landmark *Brown v. Board of Education* (1954),³² the Civil Rights Movement engaged the federal courts to dismantle the *de jure* infrastructure of segregation.³³ Yet, with every milestone — the Little Rock Nine, the March on Washington, the Civil Rights Acts — a backlash followed. This reactionary current moved from Nixon’s “Southern Strategy” to Reagan’s “welfare queens” and the 1994 “Contract with America,” such fractious politics all serving to strengthen the legal and political benefits to America’s wealthiest families.³⁴

²⁵ See HENRY LOUIS GATES, JR., *STONY THE ROAD: RECONSTRUCTION, WHITE SUPREMACY, AND THE RISE OF JIM CROW* (2019).

²⁶ Rutherford B. Hayes, Inaugural Address, March 5, 1877 (Online at Rutherford B. Hayes Presidential Library, at <https://www.rbhayes.org/hayes/rutherford-b.-hayes-s-inaugural-address/> (Last visited February 3, 2026).

²⁷ See *Plessy v. Ferguson*, 163 U.S. 537 (1898).

²⁸ See PATRICIA SULLIVAN, *LIFT EVERY VOICE: THE NAACP AND THE MAKING OF THE CIVIL RIGHTS MOVEMENT* (2009). For a vivid depiction of this work, see *Marshall* (Reginald Hudlin, dir., 2017). Chadwick Boseman plays a young Thurgood Marshall.

²⁹ See, e.g., *American Civil Liberties Union v. Mabus*, 719 F. Supp. 1345 (S.D. Miss. 1989), app'l 911 F.2d 1066, rem'd 969 F.Supp. 403, aff'd 84 F.3d 784, cert. den. 519 U.S. 992 (1996) (Mississippi Sovereignty Commission, 1954-1971, held unconstitutional for many, many reasons).

³⁰ *Guinn v. United States*, 238 U.S. 347 (1915).

³¹ *Sweatt v. Painter*, 339 U.S. 629 (1950).

³² 347 U.S. 483 (1954).

³³ See STEVEN KASHER, *THE CIVIL RIGHTS MOVEMENT: A PHOTOGRAPHIC HISTORY, 1954-68* (1996).

³⁴ See G. WILLIAM DOMHOFF, *WHO RULES AMERICA? THE TRIUMPH OF THE CORPORATE RICH* (8TH ED. 2021).

Many U.S. observers believed the 2008 election of Barack Obama would inaugurate a decolonial transition, and to an extent once began, with a wave of symbolic reckoning, including the removal of Confederate monuments and the opening of the National Museum of African American History and Culture.³⁵ However, the Obama era also fertilized the rise of internet conspiracy groups and the MAGA movement.

Under the presidential administrations of 2017 and 2025, backlash became policy,³⁶ manifesting in direct assault on affirmative action, gutting civil rights enforcement, and waging a relentless campaign to sanitize museum exhibits and school curricula that contradicted an historical narrative celebrating the American colonial focus.³⁷ Today, despite the rise of Black office holders, the wealth chasm between families of color and white families remains nearly as wide as it was in the days of old Jim Crow,³⁸ proving that while the statutes have changed, the colonialist project's echoes hollowly but persistently.

³⁵ See, e.g., JOHN JOST, *THE OBAMAS AND A (POST) RACIAL AMERICA?* (2011).

³⁶ See PIPPA NORRIS & RONALD INGLEHART, *CULTURAL BACKLASH: TRUMP, BREXIT, AND AUTHORITARIAN POPULISM* (2019).

³⁷ Enjoining the U.S. Department of the Interior to restore signage and displays removed or altered pursuant to Executive Order No. 14253, *Restoring Truth and Sanity to American History*, 2025 Fed. Reg. 05838 (March 27, 2025), the U.S. District Judge found:

“In recent months, the Government has torn down exhibits in Philadelphia’s Independence National Historical Park memorializing the legacy of people enslaved by the country’s first President; removed signage detailing climate threats at Fort Sumter in South Carolina, one of the most environmentally endangered sites in the country; and wiped away descriptions of history and science at countless National Parks across the United States.”

Nat. Parks. Cons’n Assoc. v. U.S. Dept. Interior, No. 1:26-CV-10877-AK 2025-05838 (D. Mass., June 12, 2026) (Kelley, J.), noting several of these exhibits were ordered restored in *City of Philadelphia v. Burgum*, 820 F. Supp. 3d 313 (E.D. Pa. 2026) (Rufe, J.), (Pacer Doc. 095113751206).

³⁸ In 2023, the U.S. Federal Reserve’s Survey of Consumer Finances found that the gap in wealth between the median white household and the median Black household was \$240,120, with ratio of Black family wealth at 15% of white family wealth.

Andre M. Perry, Hannah Stephens, and Manann Donoghoe, *Black Wealth is Increasing, But So is the Racial Wealth Gap*, Brookings Research (January 9, 2024) (<https://www.brookings.edu/articles/black-wealth-is-increasing-but-so-is-the-racial-wealth-gap/>).

The race gap in wealth in 1950 was only 1% higher. See Ellora Derenoncourt, Chi Hyun Kim, Moritz Kuhn & Moritz Schularick, *Wealth of Two Nations: The U.S. Racial Wealth Gap, 1860–2020*, Institute Working Paper 29, Opportunity & Inclusive Growth Institute, U.S. Federal Reserve (June 10, 2022) (<https://doi.org/10.21034/iwp.59>).